

PRODUCTION OF FUNCTIONAL BREAD PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT *This article is aimed at studying the methods of enriching flour products with vitamin-mineral mixtures and controlling their amount, which are the most important food raw materials, in order to further stabilize the quality and safety of food in our country. In addition, the relevance and importance of wheat flour in the national economy and the quality indicators of wheat flour. The production of food products from wheat flour for various consumption and the role of gluten are presented.*

Key words: *Food quality, food safety, high grade flour, first grade flour, micronutrients, micronutrient deficiency, iron deficiency (anemia), chemical methods of analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

After our country gained independence, great importance was attached to the production of consumer goods, which is the main direction of ensuring the well-being of the population. In particular, rapid development of agriculture and animal husbandry in providing the population with high-quality food products was set as a priority task. Because the importance of food products in meeting the material needs of a person as a biological being is incomparable. It is the person who receives protein, fat, carbohydrates, vitamins, mineral salts and other various compounds necessary for his life activities through food products.

In the years of independence, on the basis of the rapid development of the agricultural sector, significant progress was made in meeting the population's

demand for high-quality food products, but achieving a complete solution to these issues remains one of the urgent problems today.

For this reason, on the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947, adopted on February 7, 2017, "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "2017-2021 Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" In the third "Priority directions of economic development and liberalization" of the "Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions", deepening of structural changes in this area and consistent development of agricultural production, further strengthening of the country's food security, expanding the production of environmentally friendly products, significantly increasing the export potential of the agrarian sector, reducing the area of cotton and grain crops, planting potatoes, vegetables and oilseed crops on vacant land, as well as the placement of new intensive orchards and vineyards. great attention is paid to optimization issues.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Food safety is the absence of toxic, carcinogenic, mutagenic or any other adverse effects on the human body when consumed in permitted quantities, and the harmful effects of food products on humans and future generations. is a condition indicating the absence of an impermissible risk associated with its presentation.

Cereal crops are a source of protein and carbohydrates for human consumption and an excellent raw material for the production of high-quality mixed feed products. In addition to proteins and carbohydrates, grain and grain processing products are also an important source of a number of vitamins and minerals.

Another advantage of grain and grain products is that they do not require excessive expenses for storing grain under normal conditions for several years and transporting it over long distances.

The fact that grains and grain products make up the majority of food products grown and processed for human consumption further increases the demand for these products.

Bread, which is a grain product, provides the body with proteins and carbohydrates, and enriches it with magnesium, phosphorus, and potassium, which are necessary for brain activity. Bread contains vitamins. According to medical scientists, adults should eat 300-500 g of bread per day, those engaged in physical labor should eat 700 g, and children and teenagers should eat 150-400 g of bread. 50% of the human body's need for group B vitamins is met through bread.

Bread contains 40% to 45% carbohydrates, which means it provides the body with 10001100 calories per day. Humans get almost half of their daily energy from bread, and nothing can replace bread in human life [3].

Flour, which is the main raw material for making bread, is a product obtained by grinding or weighing (grinding) grain. During the milling process, the bran and bran are separated from the grain, and the endosperm is crushed (crushed) to the required level. The main part of the grain produced by the state is processed to obtain flour.

Flour is divided into wheat, rye, barley, oat corn, rice flour and other types, depending on which grain it is obtained from.

Flour is a raw material for a number of sectors of the food industry, primarily baking, confectionery and pasta industry. The main types of flour are wheat and rye flour. About 90% of the total produced flour corresponds to wheat flour. According to its properties and preparation technology, flour is divided into bread flour and pasta flour.

The type of flour is determined by the amount of flour obtained from 100 kg of grain. The higher the yield, the lower its grade. High, first, second and jaidari flours are obtained from wheat grain, elanma, sidarma and jaidari flour are obtained from rye grain.

During the production of flour in mills, flour is enriched with vitamins, folic acid and iron. These substances are added at the final stage so that they do not lose their value during processing, and are thoroughly mixed, so that as a result, even one squeeze contains all the nutrients. Food, bread and other products made from enriched flour do not lose their properties, and there are no changes in taste. Enriched flour retains up to 95% of its nutrients during the baking process.

Taking into account that flour products are the most important raw materials in the production of food products, by the Standardization Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan 3 on April 11, 2021, Own DSt 1104:2021 "High and first grade baking steam enriched with vitamin-mineral mixture 7 doy uni. Technical conditions" standard has been adopted.

Vitamins, minerals and trace elements play an important role in the human body. Micronutrients are irreplaceable nutrients (vitamins and minerals) necessary for the normal growth and development of the human body, which include microminerals and vitamins that the human body cannot produce on its own. .

Micronutrients play an important role in metabolism, the functioning of the human brain and nervous system, the prevention of blood clotting and the development of the immune system.

In a word, no process in the human body takes place without the participation of trace elements. Inadequate availability of macro and micronutrients in the composition of food products poses a serious threat to human health, that is, it causes physical fatigue, mental tension, nervousness, stress, and an increase in the body's susceptibility to various diseases.

Lack of micronutrients - due to the lack of micronutrients that the human body receives with food, it leads to the development of diseases.

To prevent this, the amount of micronutrients in bread and bakery products is controlled and standardized. Regular addition of microelements to the human diet is a simple and very effective way to preserve and strengthen health. Enriched

food product is a food product enriched (fortified) with micronutrients during the production process.

Flour enriched with vitamin-mineral mixture (VMA) - high and first grade bakery wheat flour enriched with vitamin-mineral mixture during flour production.

Iron is the most difficult micronutrient to include in food and absorb adequately. The choice of iron compounds for bread enrichment by scientists is characterized by the fact that it is, on the one hand, the highest biological supplement, and on the other hand, it does not violate the organoleptic quality of the enriched product.

First of all, the choice falls on soluble compounds, for example, iron sulfate, iron fumarate, elemental iron or iron phosphate can be good alternatives.

Children and women often suffer from inadequate supply of vitamins C, B2, B6, B12 and folic acid, which is necessary for its absorption, and insufficient intake of iron from food products. remains the main reason for the spread of hidden (latent) and open forms of anemia (anemia).

Therefore, the most effective solution is to enrich food products with iron and vitamins as a necessary factor and solution for successful elimination of iron deficiency. Amount of micronutrients in high and first-grade baker's wheat flour enriched with VMA in accordance with Appendix 7 of the Special Technical Regulation of the Decision No. TR-21 of January 29, 2021 "On the Safety of Grain Processing Products" of the "Uzstandart" Agency is required to be as follows

The work to create the ground for growing a high and stable crop of grain in 2022 was started last year. For the harvest of 2022 in our republic, planting of autumn grain crops on 1 million 33.1 thousand hectares of irrigated areas was carried out in September-October last year. In our country, it is important to pay special attention to grain quality indicators along with increasing grain yield.

CONCLUSION

The work of specialists who assess the organoleptic properties of flour is complex and responsible, because specialists have to pick up the smallest shades of taste and smell. The color of the flour is an indicator of its freshness and quality. The higher the grade of flour, the lighter it is because it contains less bran.

The color of flour of different varieties must meet the requirements of the standards: grains must have a white or yellowish color; the highest grade has a white or white-cream color; the first type is cream with a white or yellowish tint; the second is white with a yellowish or gray tint; the second - a variety of durum wheat - cream yellow with a yellow tint or white with a gray tint and clearly visible bran particles. Good quality wheat flour has a slightly distinct taste and smell. Soluble carbohydrates, free amino acids and organic acids in flour contribute to the aroma and taste of fresh flour.

Production of various products for human consumption from wheat grain. In order to obtain a high grade of wheat flour for the population, good storage and practical and correct analyzes in the laboratories of grain-combinations. Production of quality flours that meet republican standards. It is desirable to correctly determine the quality of wheat gluten by drawing correct conclusions.

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